

1 **Clone-specific phenotypic plasticity under constant darkness and competition reveals**
2 **surprising aphid resilience**

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26 **Statement of contribution**

27 All authors wrote the manuscript.

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30 **Mouhammad Shadi Khudr (MSK)** conceived and designed the experiment, co-performed the
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33 **Conrado Guerrero Quiles (CGQ)** did the protein analysis with YZY and provided interpretations of
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35 **Hawa Jahan (HJ)** did the C:N analysis and provided interpretations for the C:N data. HJ also
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37 aphids.

38 **Abdullatif Alfutimie (AA)** provided guidance and insights on the metabolomics analysis and
39 contributed to the writing and production of the final draft of the manuscript.

40 **Reinmar Hager (RH)** hosted the work and provided insights on the development of the analyses
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56 **Abstract**

57 Phenotypic plasticity enables phloem-feeding insects to cope with changes in their environments
58 and manifests differently across aphid lineages. Aphids show a high degree of plasticity, yet, to what
59 extent aphid reproductive and ontogenetic plasticity can stretch under extreme environmental
60 challenges remains largely unknown. In this study, we deprived parthenogenetic clones of the pea
61 aphid, *Acyrtosiphon pisum*, and black bean aphid, *Aphis fabae*, of light rhythmicity for 11 days on
62 faba bean seedlings raised in the dark to test their stress responses. We also observed the effects
63 of intra- and interspecific competition, as an added layer of stress adversity, on a target pea-aphid
64 clone (N116) under extreme phenological and nutritional conditions. Overall, there was a clone-
65 specific stress response, with a large decline in reproductive success of the pea aphids contrary to
66 the black bean aphid (BB). In competition, the N116 pea-aphid clone had the highest reproductive
67 success against its conspecific clone (N127). Further, Heat Shock Protein 70 (HSP70), as a measure
68 of a molecular stress response, was more abundant in constant darkness across all single clones,
69 particularly in N116. Interestingly, HSP70 levels for N116 were the highest in the dark without
70 competition, while the levels under competition were higher against N127 than BB. Additionally,
71 metabolomic changes occurred under stress across clones, with differences in lipids and
72 carbohydrates in N116 with and without intra- or inter-specific competition. Compared to normal
73 conditions, only N116 showed a higher C:N ratio in the dark when alone, as its ratios were always
74 higher under competition, especially against N127. Our findings suggest unexpected varying aphid
75 resilience and survival on etiolated host plants deprived of light and light rhythmicity, thus providing
76 new insights into aphid phenotypic plasticity under extreme environmental conditions.

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78 **Keywords**

79 Pea aphid, faba bean, extreme conditions, lack of light-dark rhythmicity, black bean aphid,
80 phenotypic plasticity, intra/interspecific interactions

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89 Introduction

90 The pea aphid *Acyrtosiphon pisum* (Harris) and black bean aphid *Aphis fabae* (Scopoli) are
91 polymorphic phloem-feeding insects that exist in complexes with different life histories and biotypes
92 (Lees 1966; Dixon 1977; Coeur d'acier et al. 2004; Caillaud and Losey 2010). These aphids infest a
93 wide range of plants including faba bean *Vicia faba* (L.) (Blackman and Eastop 2000), a global food
94 staple (L'Hocine et al. 2020). Pea and black bean aphids can co-exist on the faba bean host, whilst
95 they reproduce exponentially via parthenogenesis, with a short generation time under favourable
96 conditions (Dixon 1977; Van Emden and Harrington 2007). This, therefore, usually results in
97 deteriorating plant conditions and considerable crop damages (Van Emden and Harrington 2007;
98 Sandhi and Reddy 2020).

99 Being plant parasitises, aphids are dependent on the phloem sap of the host plant, as they
100 are sensitive to chemical changes in their hosts (Dixon 1977; Bell et al. 2012; Ríos Martínez and
101 Costamagna 2018). Aphids respond to environmental stress, e.g., poor nutrition as well as crowding,
102 by producing winged morphs (Dixon 1977; Whitman and Agrawal 2009) or changing body colour
103 (Wang et al. 2019). These are forms of discrete phenotypic plasticity that are energetically costly
104 and associated with reduced fecundity but have survival payoffs (Dixon 1977; Whitman and Agrawal
105 2009). Moreover, aphid fitness varies in line with their genetic variability (Khudr et al. 2014; Lu et al.
106 2016; Ma et al. 2019) and is also affected by aphid intra- and interspecific competition (Fuller et al.
107 2002; Khudr et al. 2014; Khudr et al. 2017). Aphid clones that can cope better with environmental
108 stress may have a survival advantage (Khudr et al. 2014; Lu et al. 2016; Khudr et al. 2017).

109 Studying reoccurring events and associated changes in the life cycle of aphids can further
110 our understanding of their phenology and ecology (Vilhar et al. 2013; Joschinski et al. 2016; Nature
111 portfolio 2021). The 24h behavioural or physiological rhythms of insects synchronise with, entrain to,
112 and are photo-induced by, external time-giving cues, i.e., Zeitgebers or planetary environmental
113 rhythms such as light (Numata et al. 2015; Heyde and Oster 2019; Beer and Helfrich-Förster 2020;
114 Schmal et al. 2020; Saunders 2021). The relevance and effectiveness of light, as a *Zeitgeber*, varies
115 depending on geolocation, seasonality, and organism chronobiology and lifestyle (Beer and Helfrich-
116 Förster 2020; Schmal et al. 2020). Despite being diurnal with evidence of having circadian
117 rhythmicity when reared artificially separate from their host plants (Joschinski et al. 2016; Joschinski
118 et al. 2015), aphids, as plant parasites, are dependent on the phloem sap of the host plant. It is
119 thought that they synchronise with the rhythm of their host plants more than being entrained by
120 photoperiods (Joschinski et al. 2016). However, longer exposure to darkness can induce the
121 expression of some clock genes in aphids (Cortés et al. 2010), as aphid photoperiodic responses
122 can be classified as a function of their circadian system (Cortés et al. 2010), but see (Hillman 1973).
123 Low or deficient light conditions, compared to normal light, have been shown by Dancewicz et al.
124 (2018) to negatively affect common pea *Pisum sativum* (L.) and a dependent clonal mix of the pea
125 aphid. In their study, aphid numbers plummeted in darkness, which was attributable to reduced

126 saccharides and other essential nutrients in the plant sap resulting from compromised
127 photosynthesis. Plants that develop deprived of light experience severe changes in their features
128 and properties including chlorosis, and etiolated plant growth, as the plant becomes weak, pale and
129 elongated with no expansion of embryonic leaves and undifferentiated chloroplast precursors under
130 poor light conditions (Chory et al. 1996, Arsovski et al. 2012). As such, certain fitness costs associate
131 with limited exposure to daylight in phloem-feeding pests such as aphids (Joschinski et al. 2015;
132 Joschinski et al. 2016) and the effects may be more dramatic in the long run (Joschinski et al. 2015).
133 To date, limited information is available on aphid phenological plastic responses to severe changes
134 in life-cycle events (Joschinski et al. 2015) and the absence of essential *Zeitgebers*, namely
135 deprivation of light rhythmicity, especially when aphid communities interact on a mutual host

136 Heat Shock Proteins (HSPs), e.g., HSP70, are stress-inducible and highly conserved (Feder
137 and Hofmann 1999; Yu et al. 2015; Zhao et al. 2019; Zhou et al. 2020), with housekeeping functions,
138 as they are part of the Protein Quality System (PQC) that is key to maintain homeostasis (Sørensen
139 et al. 2003). The expression of the HSP genes is largely thought to be a general process against a
140 range of stressors (Feder and Hofmann 1999; Sørensen et al. 2003; Yu et al. 2015; Zhou et al.
141 2020), leading to increased levels of HSPs (Nguyen et al. 2009; Zhao and Jones 2012). However,
142 little is known about their functionality in response to severe adversities, such as constant darkness,
143 as only few studies have explored the effects of light on HSPs (Barua and Heckathorn 2006), and
144 even fewer looked at the effects of the continuous absence of light. Integrating metabolomic analyses
145 in examining phenotypic as well as molecular responses to stressors has started to attract attention
146 in plants (Arbona et al. 2013; Bueno and Lopes 2020) but information on aphids in this regard is thus
147 far lacking. Fourier Transform InfraRed spectroscopy (FTIR) is a promising rapid transversal non-
148 destructive technique (Allwood et al. 2008; Arbona et al. 2013). FTIR analysis helps metabolically
149 characterise chemical footprints (Corte et al. 2015; Razzaq et al. 2019) of organismal responses to
150 various environmental stressors (Lankadurai et al. 2013; Baker et al. 2014; Dias et al. 2016; Allwood
151 et al. 2021; Durak et al. 2021). Profiling primary metabolites under extreme abiotic stress, especially
152 when genetic variability is a factor, could help us gain further insights into stress tolerance in insect
153 pests.

154 The literature is rich with examples of plant responses to aphid infestation (e.g., Arbona, et
155 al. 2013; Jakobs et al. 2018; Bueno and Lopes, 2020), but surprisingly, combining phenotypic,
156 metabolomic and proteomic analytics in studying aphid responses to extreme stress is
157 underdeveloped despite the affordability and ease of application. A juxtaposed illustration of stress
158 responses at different levels can corroborate our understanding of the eco-evolutionary ecology of
159 plant-pest systems. In this exploratory laboratory assay, we raised two pea aphid clones and one
160 clone of black bean aphid on one cultivar of faba bean and tested their responses to extreme
161 complex light absence and competition stress. The former was constant darkness, *i.e.*, lack of light
162 rhythmicity signifying the absence of light as a *Zeitgeber*, where N116 (target pea aphid clone) was

163 alone or in competition with a conspecific or a heterospecific as a second stressor. Our main
164 hypotheses were: 1) Aphid reproductive success will decline in the absence of light and this will differ
165 across aphid clones. 2) The clone-specific responses to constant darkness are detectable on
166 phenotypic and molecular levels.

167 **Methods**

168 *Model organisms*

169 Two aphid species were used: one clone (BB, hereafter) of black bean aphid *A. fabae*, raised
170 from a sample collected on goosefoot *Chenopodium sp.*, Manchester, UK; and two clones (green
171 and pink, N116 and N127, respectively, hereafter) of pea aphid *A. pisum*, each raised from samples
172 acquired from Imperial College (Colin Turnbull, London, UK). We started aphid stock cultures from
173 one parthenogenetic individual raised on *Vicia faba* var *minor* (Herz), whilst the Sutton dwarf heritage
174 variety of *Vicia faba* var *major* (Herz) was used for the experimental work. We sowed the faba beans
175 individually in plastic pots (8.5 cm diameter and 10 cm depth) filled with steam-sterilised soil
176 (Levington Advance Seed & Modular F2 Compost).

177 *Set-up*

178 We designed the experiment to test extreme environmental conditions of constant darkness
179 (24h night, at 22°C), signifying the absence of light rhythmicity as a *Zeitgeber*, on aphid reproductive
180 phenotypic plasticity and physiology (metabolic changes) and levels of HSP70, when aphid clones
181 were alone or in pairwise competition. We maintained the dark conditions in a controlled growth
182 cabinet for the whole period of the experimentation from seed sowing until data collection. The plants
183 were only temporarily taken out individually of the cabinet for enclosing before infestation, but this
184 was completed for each plant quickly in very dim light. Under the same conditions, watering took
185 place every two days by squirting tap water into the individual microcosm trays. A negative control
186 treatment was also set up under a normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night, 22°C) in a separate
187 controlled growth cabinet. The microcosms were made of 2-L transparent polyethylene terephthalate
188 (PET) bottles fitted with ultra-fine mesh-top for ventilation. The plant was infested with ten aphids
189 (2nd instar) of a single clone or (5+5, 2nd instar) when competing against another clone. We introduced
190 the respective aphids into the corresponding microcosms 12 days after germination, using small
191 plastic loading boats placed onto compressed soil surface adjacent to the plant stem per pot;
192 infestation lasted for 11 days (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S1). The rationale of the experiment
193 was to test the response of three different aphid clones to complex extreme stress, with the pea
194 aphid N116 being the target clone. We also measured the response of N116, as a focal clone, with
195 and without competition with its respective counterparts (N127 [conspecific], or BB [heterospecific]).
196 The reference system was the control: infestation with N116, under a normal light-dark cycle (16h
197 Day:8h Night).

198 Under normal conditions, there were 180 aphids = single clones (3 aphid clones X 3 repeats
199 X 10 aphid 2nd instars per microcosm), and competition (3 aphid competition scenarios X 3 repeats

200 X 10 aphid 2nd instars per microcosm). Under the constant absence of light and light rhythmicity,
201 there were 360 aphids = single clones (3 aphid clones X 6 repeats X 10 aphid 2nd instars per
202 microcosm), and competition (3 competition scenarios X 6 repeats X [5+5] aphid 2nd instars per
203 microcosm), (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S1). Due to the extreme adversity of the atypical
204 conditions of the experiment, the host plants were subject to etiolation and chlorosis and thus the
205 plant-aphid system crashed repeatedly. We, therefore, replicated the treatments in the absence of
206 light until the aforementioned sample sizes were reached.

207 *Measurements and analyses*

208 Phenotypic responses

209 The pea aphid N116 was the focal aphid clone in this study. We investigated aphid responses
210 to complex stress of being raised on faba bean grown in a novel severe environment of constant
211 darkness, *i.e.*, lack of light rhythmicity/the absence of light as a *Zeitgeber*, where N116 was subject
212 to intra-specific or inter-specific competition. On the 11th day, we counted aphid numbers per
213 microcosm including any winged morphs. We also examined aphid change in colouration at the bio-
214 imaging facility, the Faculty of Biology, Medicine and Health, The University of Manchester. This was
215 done by quantifying the body colour of one individual aphid per treatment using a Leica M205 FA
216 fluorescence stereomicroscope, followed by image analysis by Image J ver.1.53e for analysing the
217 values of RGB channels (RGB for red, green, blue, respectively).

218 Further, we characterised any changes in the expression and abundance of HSP70 in the
219 focal aphid clone (N116) as a proxy of aphid physiological response to the stress conditions, *i.e.*, the
220 absence of light rhythmicity and aphid competition. We also investigated any possible metabolomic
221 changes in N116 under stress; details are provided below.

222 Stress protein responses

223 Lysate production, protein quantification and Western Blotting

224 We applied western blotting as a proteomic technique (Mishra et al. 2017) to study changes
225 in HSP70 levels across the conditions of the experiment. Protein solution samples were obtained
226 using Pierce IP Lysis Buffer (ThermoFisher Scientific, Massachusetts, USA) in combination with a
227 pestle and mortar for the lysis of the aphids. Three aphid individuals were used in each extraction
228 with a total of three biological repeats. Aphid samples were sonicated and then centrifuged for debris
229 removal. The protein concentration of the samples was calculated using Pierce BCA Protein Assay
230 Kit (ThermoFisher Scientific, Massachusetts, USA), following the manufacturer's instructions.
231 Samples were separated by SDS-PAGE (45 min, 200V), (4-12% Bis-Tris gels, Thermo Fisher
232 Scientific) and transferred to nitrocellulose membrane (10h, 30V, 4°C) (Whatman, Maidstone, UK).
233 Membranes were blocked for 1h at room temperature using casein-blocking buffer (Sigma-Aldrich,
234 Missouri, USA, 1:10 dilution) in TBST (10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 0.05% [wt/vol] Tween-
235 20). Membranes were incubated with HSP70 3A3 monoclonal mouse primary ab (Thermo Fisher,

236 1:1000 dilution) on blocking buffer overnight at 4°C. Subsequently, membranes were washed three
237 times for 5 min per wash using TBST and then incubated with polyclonal goat anti-mouse secondary
238 Alexa Fluor 680 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Massachusetts, USA, 1:10000 dilution) on blocking buffer
239 in the dark at room temperature for 2h. Membranes were washed again three times for 5 min per
240 wash using TBST, then scanned using Odyssey Infrared Imaging System (LI-COR Biosciences,
241 Nebraska, USA) at 700 nm. Band signal intensity was determined based on the median pixel
242 intensity signal of the bands using Odyssey software (LI-COR Biosciences, Nebraska, USA). The
243 intensity represents the presence and level of HSP70 per sample across treatments. The
244 baseline/reference was the N116 clone alone under a normal light-dark cycle. We obtained the mean
245 (3793) of the intensities belonging to this baseline treatment under normal conditions and divided
246 the respective median pixel intensities of each of the other sample repeats by the baseline mean
247 (fold change), few outliers were removed. Subsequently, we obtained the means for the group of
248 repeats, and then we calculated the percentages of the respective means relative to the mean of the
249 baseline. This provided a relative measure of HSP70 across treatments.

250 Metabolomic responses

251 We sampled one aphid individual from each of the experimental combinations,
252 (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S1) and stored them at -80°C for analysis using Vertex 70 Fourier-
253 Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) at the Department of Chemical Engineering (CE), The
254 University of Manchester. We ran three FTIR tests per sample and selected the clearest outcome.
255 The primary focus was on the following wavelength ranges 3500-2700 cm⁻¹ associated with lipids,
256 1800-1400 cm⁻¹ signifying protein conformation, and 1200-900 cm⁻¹ signifying carbohydrates and
257 nucleic acids (Correia et al. 2016).

258 Aphid Carbon: Nitrogen (C:N) ratio

259 We pooled six aphid individuals from the three replicates per treatment, following a method
260 provided by Karley et al. (2002); the samples were oven-dried at 65°C for 48h. All the samples were
261 then ball-milled into fine powders and weighed using a microbalance. Total available carbon (C) and
262 nitrogen (N) contents of the dried and weighted samples were determined using Vario EL cube
263 elemental analyzer (Isoprime, Elementar) by gas chromatography.

264 Plant dry weight, chlorophyll quantification, and Carbon: Nitrogen (C:N) ratio

265 We further measured the dry weight of the shoot and the root at the end of the experiment
266 after drying the whole plant in a 40°C oven for three days. Moreover, we used USB4000 UV-Vis Fiber
267 Optic Spectrometer to analyse the plant chlorophyll, as 0.30g of plant leaves (pooled from three
268 replicates) per treatment was used in the analysis, with three readings on the spectrometer.
269 Furthermore, consistent cuttings carved from the terminal plant leaves per treatment were collected
270 and dried for obtaining the plant C:N ratio based on the aforementioned method.

271 *Statistical analysis*

272 We conducted the statistical analysis in R version 4.0.4 (R Core Team 2021), 'multcomp'
273 package (Hothorn et al. 2008). With a focus on our target clone N116, we divided the analysis into
274 two perspective sets:

275 First, we tested the respective clonal aphid total numbers in the microcosm on the 11th day,
276 representing aphid reproductive success. We applied a generalised linear model (GLM1) with a
277 quasiPoisson family due to the non-normal distribution of the count data. The response variable was
278 the total number of aphids in the microcosm on day 11. The predictors were 1) Light regime (a
279 categorical variable of two levels (normal light-dark cycle [baseline], and constant darkness), 2)
280 Aphid clone (a categorical variable of three levels (pea aphid N116 [baseline], conspecific N127, and
281 heterospecific BB), 3) The interaction (Light regime X Aphid clone), 4) Shoot:Root dry weight (SRW,
282 hereafter), a numerical covariate variable.

283 Second, we tested the total numbers of N116 as the focal clone in the microcosm on the 11th
284 day, representing reproductive success, with and without intra- and inter-specific competition. The
285 starting population for the competition was ten instars (five instars for each competitor), thus the total
286 aphid numbers in the single clone group were halved for the statistical analysis. We applied a
287 generalised linear model (GLM2) with a quasiPoisson family due to the non-normal distribution of
288 the data. The predictors were 1) Light regime (as above), 2) Clonal interaction status (a categorical
289 variable of three 3 levels (N116 alone [baseline], N116 against the conspecific clone N127
290 [intraspecific competition], N116 against the heterospecific clone BB [interspecific competition]), 3)
291 Competitor density (a numerical variable representing the total number of the respective aphid clone
292 competing with N116 in the microcosm), 4) The interaction (Light regime X Clonal interaction status),
293 5) SRW. The main effects of the models are shown using an Anova command, R package 'car' (Fox
294 and Weisberg 2019).

295 **Data**

296 The data of this study are available in "figshare" at
297 <https://figshare.com/s/597ae5ca0d886102f82d>

298

299 **Results**

300 Clone-specific differences between light and dark treatment

301 Aphid clone and the interaction between aphid clone and the absence of light-dark regime
302 significantly influenced aphid reproductive success ($F_{(2,20)} = 6.63$, $P = 0.006$) and ($F_{(2,20)} = 7.24$, $P =$
303 0.004), respectively. The effect of the covariate (SRW) was also significant ($F_{(1,20)} = 5.49$, $P = 0.03$),
304 (Supplementary Materials, Table S1). The largest difference between the normal vs darkness
305 conditions was found in N116 (~76%) followed by N127 (~49%) and then BB (~42%). However,
306 deprivation of light had a strong negative impact on the populations of the pea aphids (N116 and
307 N127 but surprisingly not on the black bean aphid (BB), as the latter heterospecific clone did ~73%

308 better under constant darkness than normal light-dark cycle. As such, BB did ~76% better than N116
 309 and ~74% better than N127, as the pea aphids had similar population counts in the dark (Fig. 1).

310 Our analysis for HSP70 revealed that, compared to baseline (HSP70 of N116 under normal
 311 light-dark cycle), BB had the lowest level of HSP70 (29% of that of the baseline), while N127 had
 312 the highest level of HSP70 (139% of the baseline) for that condition. There were considerably
 313 increased levels of HSP70 levels in constant darkness that peaked in N127 (301% of that of the
 314 baseline), followed by 282% in N116, and 105% in BB. The highest margin of difference in HSP70
 315 levels between the light regimes was in N116, followed by N127, and then BB that showed the
 316 highest reproductive success in the dark as described above. By contrast, the rise in the HSP70
 317 levels in the two pea aphid conspecifics was notable and associated with their reduced reproductive
 318 success in the dark (Fig. 1).

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320

321 **Fig 1. Aphid reproductive success under normal dark/light conditions and complete**
 322 **darkness.** We used two pea aphid clones (N116 [baseline] and N127) and one clone of black bean
 323 aphid (BB). The bars represent aphid reproductive success proxied by total aphid numbers in the
 324 microcosm (mean ±SE) under normal light-dark cycle (light grey), (N116, n = 3, N127, n = 3, BB, n
 325 = 3), and constant darkness (dark grey), (N116, n = 6, N127, n = 6, BB, n = 6). The dashed lines
 326 represent the level (mean ±SE) of HSP70 under normal conditions (orange) and constant darkness
 327 (black), signifying aphid stress response. The amount of HSP70 is proportional and relative to the
 328 quantity observed for N116 under normal conditions. L_Ph (phenotypic response [Aphid total
 329 numbers as a proxy for reproductive success] under normal conditions), NL_Ph (phenotypic
 330 response [reproductive success] under constant darkness), L_Pr (protein response [HSP70 as a
 331 proxy for molecular stress response] under normal conditions), NL_Pr (protein response [HSP70]
 332 under constant darkness entailing lack of light rhythmicity).

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336 To assess physiological responses to the complex stress conditions the FTIR results showed,
337 on a metabolomic level, that for N116 there was a clear difference in the lipid metabolites as the
338 peaks, ranging from 3500-2700 cm^{-1} , were not present under constant darkness in stark contrast
339 with the case under the normal light-dark cycle. There was an indication of protein metabolism, but
340 it was less noticeable in the dark because under normal conditions the peaks, ranging from 1800-
341 1400 cm^{-1} , were more intense. Additionally, the expression of carbohydrate and nucleic acid
342 metabolites, ranging from 1200-900 cm^{-1} , was considerably lower in the dark (Supplementary
343 Materials, Fig. S2). In the case of the conspecific N127, there was a negligible difference in the
344 changes in lipid metabolites between the two conditions of the experiment apart from the peak at
345 1740 cm^{-1} , which was absent in the dark (the same pattern in N116). As for protein metabolites, the
346 major difference was seen around wavelength 1650 cm^{-1} , as the intensity of this peak was lower
347 when N127 was raised in the dark compared to normal conditions; similar patterns were observed
348 for carbohydrates and nucleic acids (Supplementary Materials, Figs. S2 and S3). In the case of the
349 heterospecific BB, the main difference in lipid metabolism was observed around 2850 cm^{-1} , with a
350 higher peak intensity when BB was raised in the dark, opposite to the pattern seen in N116 and
351 N127 (Supplementary Materials, Figs. S2-S4). Almost no differences were observed for protein,
352 carbohydrates and nucleic acid metabolites between darkness and normal conditions for BB
353 (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S4). See also (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S5) for pictures of the
354 host plant and aphids across the light regimes of the study. As for the analysis of aphid colour
355 change, there was an RGB decrease in N116 when raised in the dark, contrary to the observations
356 in the cases of N127 and BB, with a noticeable increase in the red colour in N127, and the blue
357 colour in BB, in the dark (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S6). That is in line with the extra brightness
358 or pink vividness in N127 (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S5). See also (Supplementary Materials,
359 Fig. S7) for analysis of plant chlorophyll under the normal light-dark cycle subject to aphid presence
360 (alone or in competition).

361 Further, as an indicator of quantitative compositional changes in the aphid and host plant
362 bodies, the lowest C:N values in the dark in the plant and the aphids pertained to BB. The highest
363 ratio in aphids was found in N127 across regimes. The C:N ratio of the host plant in the dark was
364 always higher than that under a normal light-dark cycle. Only N116 had a higher C:N ratio in the dark
365 compared to the light condition (Table 1) and (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S8). N127 had the
366 highest levels of carbohydrates across light regimes, which is generally in line with the outcome of
367 the metabolomics analysis given above. By contrast, BB had the lowest level of carbohydrates in the
368 dark; note that the carbohydrate level for BB under normal conditions was between the levels of
369 N116 and N127 but that was not far from the level in the dark, (Table 1) and (Supplementary
370 Materials, Fig. S8). Additionally, under normal conditions, the C:N ratio was the lowest in the N127-
371 infested plants. The N116-infested host plant had more carbohydrates in the dark than under normal

372 conditions. Similarly, N116 had more carbohydrates in constant darkness compared to that of the
 373 normal condition (Table 1) and (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S8).

374 **Table 1. Comparison of C:N ratios in the host plant and aphids across light regimes.** The table
 375 gives the C:N ratios of single clones of aphids and the associated faba bean host plant. The light
 376 regimes were normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night), referred to as (L), and constant darkness
 377 (0h Day:24h Night), referred to as (NL), and the proportional change in C:N ratio in NL relative to L.
 378 There were three clonal aphid identities (pea aphids [N116 and N127] and black bean aphids [BB]).

	Aphid clone	Host plant
L	N116 (4.76) < BB (5.38) < N127 (7.45)	N127(4.06) < N116(4.8) < BB(5.19)
NL	BB (5.04) < N116 (5.51) < N127 (5.77)	BB(5.76) < N127(6.01) < N116(6.42)
NL to L %	N127 (77%) < BB (94%) < N116 (116%)	BB (111%) < N116 (134%) < N127 (148%)

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380 Inter and intra-specific competition effects on N116

381 The focal pea aphid clone N116 responded differently to constant light absence and the lack
 382 of light rhythmicity, which had a significant effect ($F_{(1,19)} = 11.43$, $P = 0.003$) on the reproductive
 383 success of this clone (Supplementary Materials, Table S2). Under normal conditions, N116 had a
 384 higher reproductive success compared to BB (~55% larger than what it achieved under single clone
 385 conditions), but its weakest outcome was versus the conspecific clone N127 (~19% less than under
 386 single clone conditions). Compared to N116, as a single clone under normal light conditions, the
 387 darkness treatment led to the smallest reproductive success (~76% less), followed by the case when
 388 it competed against BB (~65% less). In constant darkness, N116 had the greatest reproductive
 389 success when competing with N127, (Fig. 2). As such, inter-clonal interaction on the shared host
 390 was influenced by the identity of the competitor being a conspecific or a heterospecific (Khudr et al.
 391 2017).

392 Our analysis for HSP70 showed that compared to the baseline (HSP70 of N116 under a
 393 normal light-dark cycle), there was a considerable increase of 189% when N116 was in intraspecific
 394 competition with N127. That decreased to (114%) when N116 was in interspecific competition with
 395 BB. The N116 levels of HSP70 were consistently higher in constant darkness than the normal light-
 396 dark cycle, but there was a steep decline moving from the case of N116 as a single clone (282%) to
 397 (201%) against N127, then (127%) against BB. Moreover, the largest margin of difference in HSP70
 398 levels between the dark and the normal conditions was seen when N116 was alone, as the
 399 differences in the case of the intraspecific competition were quite small. Although the difference in
 400 HSP70 levels under interspecific competition followed a similar pattern, the drop in aphid
 401 reproductive success in the dark was dramatic against BB, (Fig. 2).

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405 **Fig 2. N116 reproductive success under normal dark/light conditions and complete darkness,**
 406 **subject to competition.** The bars represent the means (\pm SE) of the total numbers of the pea aphid
 407 N116 (a proxy for reproductive success) in the microcosm on the 11th day. N116 was present as a
 408 single clone [N116 alone], in intraspecific competition (vs N127), or interspecific competition with
 409 black bean aphid (vs BB). The grey bars represent the reproductive success under a normal light-
 410 dark cycle (light grey), (N116 alone, $n = 3$). Whereas, the black bars represent the reproductive
 411 success under constant darkness (dark grey), (6 repeats \times 3 interaction scenarios). Faba bean was
 412 the host plant. In the case of N116 alone as a single clone in the microcosm, aphid total numbers
 413 were halved as specified in the Methods above. The dashed lines represent the quantified quantity
 414 (mean \pm SE) of HSP70 of N116 under a normal light-dark cycle (orange) and constant darkness
 415 (black), signifying the response of N116 to physical stress with and without competition (intra- or
 416 inter-specific). The quantity of HSP70 is proportional relative to the quantity corresponding to that of
 417 N116 alone under normal conditions. L_Ph (phenotypic response [Aphid total numbers as a proxy
 418 for reproductive success] under normal conditions), NL_Ph (phenotypic response [reproductive
 419 success] under constant darkness), L_Pr (protein response [HSP70 as a proxy for molecular stress
 420 response] under normal conditions), NL_Pr (protein response [HSP70] under constant darkness
 421 entailing lack of light rhythmicity).

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424 On the metabolomic level, the FTIR results showed a stark difference in lipid metabolism in
 425 the dark (wavelengths ranging from 2917 to 2850 cm^{-1}), and carbohydrates metabolism (1150-1050
 426 cm^{-1} wavelength range) in N116 under competition, especially against the conspecific N127 when
 427 compared to the single clone N116. Nevertheless, the peak intensity for lipid metabolism was higher
 428 for N116 as a single clone under normal conditions (Supplementary Materials, Figs. S2, S9 and
 429 S10). A similar pattern was observed for protein metabolism, ranging from 1652 cm^{-1} to 1300 cm^{-1} ,
 430 but the peak intensities were almost identical against both competitors (Supplementary Materials,
 Figs. S2, S9 and S10). However, under normal conditions, the peak intensity for protein metabolism

431 showed little difference between competing against N127 or BB; but it was more intense under
432 competition especially in the dark (Supplementary Materials, Figs. S2, S9-S12). The peak intensity
433 for carbohydrates metabolism, ranging from 1150 cm^{-1} to 1050 cm^{-1} , when N116 was alone with little
434 difference in the peaks between competing against N127 or BB (Supplementary Materials, Figs. S2,
435 S9-S12). That was opposite to the observation in the dark, but the results under normal conditions
436 were almost identical when N116 competed against N127 or BB (Supplementary Materials, Figs.
437 S2, S9-S12). See also (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S13) for body colour change analysis of the
438 target pea aphid clone N116 across contexts; in general, the RGB readings for green were
439 universally higher under normal conditions, when compared to those in constant darkness. This is
440 in line with the paler grade of green observed in the dark for N116 (Supplementary Materials, Fig.
441 S5). Moreover, across treatments, RGB readings were almost identical when N116 was alone or
442 competed against the conspecific N127 in the dark, while the readings were slightly higher against
443 the heterospecific BB (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S13). See also (Supplementary Materials, Fig.
444 S14) for plant chlorophyll analysis in response to the presence of N116 (alone or competing against
445 con- or heterospecifics) under a normal light-dark cycle.

446 Notably, when N116 competed with BB (compared to competing with N127), the highest
447 levels of carbohydrates were detected, with little difference across the conditions of the experiment.
448 This suggests a weak effect of the latter on carbohydrate and amino acid contents in N116.
449 Moreover, the lowest value in plant C:N, in the dark, corresponded to the case when N116 competed
450 with BB, while the lowest value in the aphids corresponded to the single clone N116 condition. Under
451 normal conditions, the plant C:N ratio was the lowest in the context where N116 competed with BB,
452 while the highest ratio was found when N116 was alone. At any rate, the C:N ratios were always
453 higher in the dark than under normal conditions for both the host plant and aphids (Table 2) and
454 (Supplementary Materials, Fig. S15). See Supplementary Materials *Note 1* (Fig. S16, Table S3, and
455 Fig. S17) for a third perspective including the analysis of aphid reproductive success and C:N ratios
456 across all clones with and without competition. See also Supplementary Materials *Note 1* (Figs. S18-
457 S20, and Table S4-S6) for further analysis of host plant traits across light regimes and treatments.

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466 **Table 2. Comparison of C:N ratios in the host plant and pea aphid N116 as a single clone or**
 467 **in competition across light regimes.** The table displays values of C:N ratios of the faba bean host
 468 plant and under aphid infestation along with the clone N116. The light regimes were normal light-
 469 dark cycle (L), and constant darkness (NL), and the proportional change in C:N ratio in NL relative
 470 to L. N116 either was alone on the plant or competed against conspecific N127 (*vs* N127) or
 471 heterospecific clone black bean aphid (*vs* BB).

	N116	Host plant
L	N116 alone (4.76) < <i>vs</i> N127 (5.44) < <i>vs</i> BB (6.98)	<i>vs</i> BB (3.99) < <i>vs</i> N127 (4.34) < N116 alone (4.80)
NL	N116 alone (5.51) < <i>vs</i> N127 (7.31) < <i>vs</i> BB (7.50)	<i>vs</i> BB (5.49) < <i>vs</i> N127 (6.18) < N116 alone (6.42)
NL to L %	<i>vs</i> BB (107%) < N116 (116%) < <i>vs</i> N127 (134%)	N116 (134%) < <i>vs</i> BB (138%) < <i>vs</i> N127 (142%)

472

473 Discussion

474 Our findings describe the striking survival of aphids deprived of light on severely etiolated
 475 host plants with a critical lack of chlorophyll. In the absence of light rhythmicity, counterintuitively,
 476 some aphids managed to develop in the dark, as aphids responded in a clone-specific manner, but
 477 with dramatic declines in their numbers that were more apparent in pea than black bean aphids.
 478 Overall, higher levels of HSP70, as an indicator of stress, were evident in the dark in the pea aphids
 479 (particularly N116) rather than in the black bean aphid. A metabolomic response across clones was
 480 clear under physical stress when compared to the patterns under the normal light-dark cycle.
 481 Moreover, only N116 showed a higher C:N ratio in the dark than the control, but N127 had the highest
 482 ratio in the dark. N116 also showed the largest population under competition with the heterospecific
 483 BB under a normal light-dark cycle, accompanied by a low HSP70 level. N116 did best against the
 484 conspecific N127 with minimal differences in reproductive success and HSP levels across the light
 485 regimes. However, in all competition contexts, N116's HSP70 levels were higher in the dark than
 486 under the normal light-dark cycle. Moreover, N116 had higher C:N ratios in the dark compared to
 487 normal light conditions and the highest margins of difference were detected when N116 competed
 488 with N127. Further, we detected noticeable differences in the metabolomic profile of N116 in the dark
 489 for lipids and carbohydrates, depending on whether in competition or not, and the type of competition
 490 (against a conspecific or a heterospecific). At any rate, it should be noted that since the temperature
 491 was stable within the favourable range for aphids and the time spent in the dark was below a certain
 492 threshold of consecutive generations (Trionnaire et al. 2009), there was no emergence of sexual
 493 morphs. Moreover, although the nutritional stress was extreme on the etiolated host plants suffering
 494 from chlorosis in the dark, wing dimorphism (polyphenism) was absent in the pea and black bean
 495 aphids. Moreover, the stable temperature, low aphid densities, and the lack of photoperiod may
 496 account for this as a sort of bet-hedging strategy (Olofsson et al. 2009; Joschinski 2016) for reduced
 497 fitness, but more opportunity for survival, through phenotypic determination on a depleted arrhythmic
 498 resource (Lees 1959; Dixon 1977; Braendle et al. 2006; Whitman and Agrawal 2009; Ogawa and
 499 Miura 2014).

500 The constant absence of light as a *Zeitgeber* led to similar reproductive success on a within-
501 species phenotypic level in the pea aphid, although the HSP70 levels suggested that the respective
502 conspecifics underwent a higher magnitude of stress when compared to the heterospecific BB.
503 However, the black bean aphid clone appeared to be more able to cope with the atypical extreme
504 stress than its pea aphid counterparts were. The interpretations of the findings of our study are
505 attributable to one or more of several factors as discussed below.

506 First, differences in endosymbiont communities and their titres. Aphids are dependent on
507 *Buchnera aphidicola*, their main heritable obligatory bacterial endosymbiont that, supported by
508 facultative endosymbionts (Burke et al. 2010; Zhang et al. 2019), enriches the limited sap diet of the
509 aphid host with essential metabolites for aphid development and survival (Douglas 1998; Baumann
510 2005; Dunbar et al. 2007). The endosymbionts transmit vertically from mothers to daughters (Burke
511 et al. 2010) and their diversity and densities may vary dependent on aphid genetic variability and
512 phenotypic variation (Feldhaar 2011) along with plant quality (Colella et al. 2018). Aphid vitality,
513 reproduction and survival are highly dependent on their endosymbionts (Douglas 1998; Dunbar et
514 al. 2007; Burke et al. 2010; Feldhaar 2011). Moreover, the functionality of *B. aphidicola* may depend
515 on the activity of other facultative endosymbionts following exposure to abiotic stress (Heyworth et
516 al. 2020; Monnin et al. 2020). It is worthy of note that *Serratia symbiotica*, a facultative endosymbiont,
517 detected in the target clone N116 (Purkiss et al. 2021) may protect the host including the primary
518 endosymbiont against thermal stress and play an important complementary nutritive role as well
519 (Zhang et al. 2019; Monnin et al. 2020). On the contrary, the conspecific N127 harbours lower
520 densities of facultative endosymbionts (personal communication Hawa Jahan, unpublished data),
521 but this requires further investigation under the extreme conditions of the current studies. The
522 unexpected ability to adapt to the extremely challenging conditions may be partly due to benefits
523 arising from the symbiotic association (Feldhaar 2011; Enders et al. 2015) as well as to differences
524 in the availability and titre of the endosymbiotic communities (Frago et al. 2012) in the studied aphid
525 clones. We, therefore, speculate that that could be extended to be the case under stressors other
526 than those used in this study.

527 Second, different expression levels or copy numbers of HSP70. As in *Drosophila*
528 *melanogaster*, differences in the expression levels of different copies across genotypes (Bettencourt
529 et al. 2008) may lead to varying outcomes of stress tolerance in aphids. The stress-inducible HSP70
530 (Zhou et al. 2020) is one of the ubiquitous HSPs essential to maintain homeostasis (King and
531 MacRae 2015) and buffer against biotic and abiotic stressors (Zhao and Jones 2012; Yu et al. 2015).
532 HSPs, such as HSP70, are upregulated in response to stressors (Ul Haq et al. 2019) and during
533 diapause (Rinehart et al. 2007; Zhao and Jones 2012); with evidence for the upregulation of HSP70
534 in both the aphid host and its primary endosymbiont in reaction to abiotic stress (Enders et al. 2015).
535 Our findings are accordant with the implication that stress resilience, due to the functionalities of
536 HSPs, appears to enhance organism adaptive properties in the face of sharp and abrupt periods of
537 stress exposure, but not when the environment merely fluctuates (Sørensen et al. 2003). For

538 instance, it has been shown in crayfish that HSP70 interacts with Hypoxia-Inducible Factor 1-alpha
539 (HIF1- α , a circadian transcription factor [Reinke et al. 2008]) under extreme light cycles and constant
540 darkness, where the proteins reciprocally affect each other (Velázquez-Amado et al. 2012). Their
541 mutual modulatory relationship contributes to crayfish predictive synchronising and hence metabolic
542 adaptation to extreme *Zeitgebers* (Velázquez-Amado et al. 2012), as HIF-1 α quantities increase
543 under constant darkness. A similar mechanism can underlie aphid molecular responses to stress
544 since HSPs play a key regulatory role in chaperoning other proteins, protecting against stress, and
545 participating in anti-apoptosis processes, in addition to being associated with energy utilisation and
546 the factors that catalyse the interconversion between the ATP and ADP (Beere 2004). HSP70 may
547 as well play a modulatory role in signal transduction under stress involving protein kinase A, protein
548 kinase C and protein phosphatase (Ding et al. 1998; Wang et al. 2004), but this needs further
549 research in plant-aphid systems. At any rate, the higher HSP70 levels detected across the aphid
550 clones and interaction scenarios in our work suggest tolerance supportive properties. That helped
551 the aphids show increased resilience or plasticity, with varying degrees of success against extreme
552 environmental changes, see also (Parsell and Lindquist 1993; Li et al. 2013; Benoit et al. 2010); see
553 also (Wang et al. 2004). In this regard, the BB clone seemed to be more resilient in the dark than
554 the pea aphid clones.

555 Third, in terms of metabolism and locomotion, aphids have an adapted diurnal lifestyle
556 (Joschinski et al. 2016; Beer et al. 2017) and are reported to show circadian rhythmicity (Cortés et
557 al. 2010; Joschinski et al. 2015), with endogenous circadian clock and considerable phenological
558 plasticity (Joschinski et al. 2015) that respond to *Zeitgebers*. That equips aphids with the ability to
559 show adaptive phenological responses (Hardie and Vaz Nunes 2001; Saunders 2002; Beer et al.
560 2017) to environmental challenges in ways that can contribute to preventing population extinction in
561 stressful environments (Hodgson and Lane 1981; Cortés et al. 2010; Chevin et al. 2013).

562 The aphids used in this experiment are descendants of aphids that had been reared for
563 hundreds of generations under a normal preferable light-dark cycle. The faba bean host plant, having
564 been germinated, grown, and aphid-infested for the duration of the experiment, in complete
565 darkness, was arrhythmic. Thus, the aphids introduced to infest the plant might have developed their
566 own rhythm associated with their entrainment by an upbringing in a maternal environment with a
567 normal rhythm preceding the experiment (Hodgson and Lane 1981). However, following the abrupt
568 shift into darkness, the aphid biological rhythm continued to oscillate for a time (Beer et al. 2017;
569 Soengas et al. 2018). Then, due to a lack of photic entrainment in the dark (Ruby et al. 2002; Kutaragi
570 et al. 2018), aphids eventually hitchhiked the plant arrhythmicity (Hodgson and Lane 1981; Soengas
571 et al. 2018). Any retarded activities in constant darkness may be a product of a dampened clock per
572 se (Hardie and Vaz Nunes 2001; Joschinski et al. 2016).

573 This also receives support from the findings suggesting that the short night internal clock
574 system in the vetch aphid *Megoura viciae* (Buckton) dampens rapidly after a few cycles under
575 constant conditions (Hardie and Vaz Nunes 2001). As the experiment lapses into constant

576 perturbation (*i.e.*, continuous absence of the *Zeitgeber*, namely light-dark rhythmicity), the aphid
577 biological rhythm may have attenuated and then stopped (Winfree 1970; Schmal et al. 2020). As
578 such, the clone-specific responses highlighted in this study can be attributed to constrained
579 phenotypic plasticity in phenology resulting from altered rhythmicity and limited day length
580 (Joschinski et al. 2015) that negatively impacted aphid performance, altered their development, and
581 hence eventually led to reduced reproductive success. That was itself influenced by aphid genotype,
582 the interaction context (single clone or competing against a conspecific or a heterospecific). We set
583 the temperature at 22°C throughout and thus the observed phenological aphid responses to the
584 absence of light are attributable to the independent circadian system rather than to photoperiodism
585 since the latter depends on extraneous factors and is highly sensitive to temperature changes
586 (Tauber and Kyriacou 2001). The expression of clock genes induces circadian rhythms by feeding
587 back to themselves (Hardin et al. 1990). However, Joschinski et al. (2016) suggested that changes
588 in plant traits, including C:N ratio and quality, due to shorter days can entrain the dependent
589 parthenogenetic aphid communities by resetting the aphid circadian clock, with negative impacts on
590 aphid reproductive success (Joschinski et al. 2015; Joschinski et al. 2016). Moreover, phenological
591 changes in aphids can lead to metabolic changes accordingly (Beer et al. 2017). As with the changes
592 in the expression of clock genes and their feedback loops due to thermal stress, *Zeitgeber* effects of
593 constant darkness on circadian rhythmicity responses, associated with changes in HSP
594 concentrations, are plausible, but our knowledge of that is still insufficient (Rensing and Monnerjahn
595 1996). It is noteworthy that it has been reported that the pink genotypes of the pea aphid, unlike the
596 green ones, being polymorphic, may have the ability to break down lipids and carotenoids to
597 compensate for carbohydrates shortage under a poor diet. This adaptive stress response to
598 malnutrition or starvation gives the pink genotypes a metabolic/energetic advantage (Wang et al.
599 2019). However, in the dark N127 was outcompeted by N116 and it experienced a higher level of
600 HSP70 and thus the role of the metabolic advantage was not clear or straightforward under extreme
601 conditions such as constant darkness.

602 Fourth, altered plant biology under stress might have been a key factor in shaping aphid
603 responses to stress. The etioplast–chloroplast transition is light dependent (Philippar et al. 2007) in
604 plants; so is the auto-control of seedling growth-associated photoreceptors (Thomas and Dickinson
605 1979; Lecharny and Jacques 1980). Depending on the amount of light available, plants usually follow
606 either of two different developmental pathways (Seluzicki et al. 2017): The first is normal light-
607 mediated development termed ‘photomorphogenesis’ that occurs under sufficient light conditions
608 where plants show normal morphological and metabolic features. The second is termed
609 ‘skotomorphogenesis’ and it refers to plant development in the dark or under poor light conditions
610 (Seluzicki et al. 2017), leading to abnormal elongated (etiolated) plant growth, decolouration, with
611 weaker stems, deformed leaves and undifferentiated chloroplast precursors (Chory et al. 1996,
612 Arsovski et al. 2012; Seluzicki et al. 2017). The plants grown in the dark in our work showed typical
613 skotomorphogenesis, as the stems were clearly weak and brittle and thus with more penetrable

614 epidermis than that of the control. This might have facilitated the piercing of the plant tissue by the
615 aphid stylets and hence aphid feeding. Further, the status of aphid interaction might have also
616 influenced the responses of the interacting aphids and hence their host plant. Interspecific
617 competition appeared to cause the least stress on N116, perhaps due to either weakened host plants
618 under dual infestation with two aphid species, or different colonisation habits as N116 and BB rarely
619 spatially mixed on their mutual host plant. Still, despite competition with BB being beneficial for N116
620 in terms of reproduction under normal conditions, the absence of light, more than the interspecific
621 competition, appeared to affect N116 more strongly in the dark. Conversely, although N116 was
622 more challenged in intraspecific competition, it had similar reproductive success across light
623 regimes, with a considerably better outcome for N116 in the dark than that against BB or in the
624 absence of competition. In the light of the evidence for changes in carbon sinks under aphid
625 infestation (Charters et al. 2020), that can be explained by a tendency of N116 not to segregate its
626 niche from its N127 conspecific. We observed a degree of clone mixing on the plant under
627 intraspecific competition, indicating reduced interference competition (Inbar et al. 1995). The mixing
628 might have exacerbated artificial metabolite sink effects (Inbar et al. 1995; Larson and Whitham
629 1997) on shared etiolated exhausted plants, which in turn benefited the target clone N116.

630 Generally, changes in the leaf carbohydrate content are reflected in the phloem sap; feeding
631 on the diluted night sap helps aphids offset the osmotic challenge of the carbohydrate-rich content
632 of the day sap (Cull and van Emden 1977; Hodgson and Lane 1981; Nalam et al. 2020). However,
633 the night sap is poorer with amino acids (Sharkey and Pate 1976). Moreover, growing in poor light
634 conditions can lead to insufficient ATP production and insufficiency in carbohydrate biosynthesis
635 (Maguire and Kobe 2015; Christiaens et al. 2016). Changes in the availability of sugars due to
636 malfunctioning/disrupted photosynthesis can affect many different aspects of plant biology and
637 metabolism, especially in the ecological context of plant-pest interactions. This is because plant
638 defence against stressors requires adequate availability of carbohydrates in the plant body
639 Dancewicz et al. (2018). Thus, the constant exposure to that sap in the dark, throughout our study,
640 increased the stress burden on the aphids and their endosymbionts that needed the sugars to
641 nurture their hosts with much-needed metabolites. Nevertheless, the very severe changes in the
642 host plant might have helped aphid survival due to weakened plant resistance. As such, the aphids
643 in our study that developed from early instars then managed to reproduce 'struggled to survive' in
644 the dark in line with the reported finding by Dancewicz et al. (2018). Our findings, therefore, merit
645 further examination of the endosymbiont densities and dynamics as well as plant metabolomic
646 changes in the constant absence of light in future work.

647 Interestingly, as specified in the C:N analysis above, the host plants infested with N116 alone
648 had the highest level of carbohydrates in constant darkness; as for the aphid N116, carbohydrate
649 levels peaked in the context of competition with BB. Furthermore, the largest difference in C:N ratios
650 between the two light regimes was observed when N116 competed with N127 and that was the case
651 for both N116 and the host plant. This is in line with the findings reported by Corbesier et al. (2002)

652 in *Sinapis alba* and *Arabidopsis thaliana* on the C:N to be higher in the dark period due to a spike in
653 the export of sucrose at night rather than in the light. Carbon is also reflective of carbon-based
654 secondary compounds that increase in plants grown in unfavourable conditions, which in turn may
655 alter the growth and development of herbivorous insects and their interactions with the plant (e.g.,
656 Coviella et al .2002). Higher C:N ratios have been linked to reduced aphid development and
657 increased survival (Karley et al. 2002; Nalam et al. 2020).

658 Although the phloem sap that was available to the studied aphids was poor in amino acids,
659 given the extreme nature of the conditions, the sap was relatively advantageous to the aphids. This
660 is because we observed lower production of honeydew that is usually excreted to counterbalance
661 the osmotic challenge of the haemolymph after diurnal feeding (Nalam et al. 2020). Aphids are more
662 hydrated after night feeding when compared to day feeding because naturally, the watery content of
663 the night sap aids in aphid rehydration and osmoregulation (Nalam et al. 2020). Furthermore, Nalam
664 et al. (2020) suggested that during night feeding aphid salivation increases leading to more
665 manipulation of the plant system and defences.

666 Our results support the findings of several studies that aphids exhibit significant genotype-
667 by-stress interactions that affect their behaviour, reproduction, and survival (Enders et al. 2015), and
668 that within-species genetic variability is characterised by differences at the phenotypic and molecular
669 levels (Enders et al. 2015). In this regard, the acquired FTIR data here complement our primary
670 findings from the perspective that reactions to extreme abiotic stress occur across multiple levels,
671 as changes in essential metabolites in the face of stress may play a role in stress tolerance (Arbona
672 et al. 2013). In our study, both the aphids and the plant were raised under severe conditions marked
673 by the lack of a day-night cycle in constant darkness, whilst each acting as a bio-stressor of the other
674 (Enders et al. 2015). The aphid N116 was extra challenged when it also competed with a conspecific
675 or a heterospecific under these conditions. The current knowledge of conspecific and heterospecific
676 interactions under severe or extreme conditions in aphid-crop systems is understudied. Our findings,
677 therefore, highlight the importance of quantifying changes in plasticity (reproductive, developmental,
678 phenotypic, and phenological) in extreme chronobiological conditions and warrant further research.

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